

Analysis of Employee Communication Ethics on The Performance of The Personnel Bureau of The General Secretary of The Ministry of Defense of The Republic of Indonesia

Wilogo Siwi Pamungkas^{1*}, Elis Yulianti²

Institut Manajemen Wiyata Indonesia

*Corresponding author: nindymahesuari@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to analyze the communication ethics of employees in the Directorate of Personnel Bureau of the Ministry of Defence of the Republic of Indonesia verbal communication, to analyze the communication ethics of employees in the Directorate of Personnel Bureau of the Ministry of Defence of the Republic of Indonesia in using nonverbal communication, and to analyze the application of communication ethics through the principles of communication ethics of employees in the Directorate of Personnel Bureau of the Ministry of Defence of the Republic of Indonesia. The method used is descriptive qualitative. Data were obtained through interviews and observations with Civil Servants (ASN) and military personnel related to this research in the Directorate of Personnel Bureau of the Ministry of Defence. The results show that (1) Employees' practice of communication ethics in the Directorate of Personnel Bureau of the Ministry of Defence of the Republic of Indonesia positively influences verbal communication, creating a harmonious work environment with polite, clear, and respectful language, and demonstrating integrity. This ethics is also evident through online media practices, strengthening effective communication and shaping a productive and ethical work environment. (2) Nonverbal communication ethics in the Directorate of Personnel Bureau of the Ministry of Defence of the Republic of Indonesia maintain integrity, credibility, and respect for ethical principles through body gestures and attitudes crucial for an efficient, harmonious work environment in line with ethical principles. Training and adaptation to workplace norms support awareness of body language and nonverbal expression, strengthening understanding of communication ethics. (3) The application of communication ethics in the Directorate of Personnel Bureau of the Ministry of Defence of the Republic of Indonesia positively impacts organizational culture, integrity, and public trust. Employees can build an inclusive, transparent, and accountable work culture by adhering to ethical principles in daily interactions, supporting organizational integrity, and positive stakeholder relations. Communication plays a vital role in organizations, especially in the Directorate of Personnel Bureau of the Ministry of Defence of the Republic of Indonesia.

Keywords: verbal communication, nonverbal communication, communication ethics.

Introduction

The Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia, as the personnel development officer at the Ministry of Defense of the

Republic of Indonesia, has the responsibility to organize the function of personnel development within the Ministry of Defense. The success of these tasks is certainly not only in understanding the technical and administrative fields but also in the ability of employees to interact in communication between employees well. Good communication certainly greatly influences performance assessments within the organizational environment and will be a challenge, especially in terms of understanding and following the norms and ethics of communication that apply to realizing the vision and mission of the organization.

Employees are often faced with complex tasks to adapt to the culture that applies to an organization. In this case, communication ethics play an important role as a guideline in daily interactions. Employees need to understand not only what is said, but also how they behave, speak, listen, and respond to communication from subordinates, colleagues and superiors.

Based on a survey conducted by researchers on the observed research objects, several phenomena occur in the work environment initiated by the communication process, including the use of slang or informal language in the work environment such as greeting superiors or colleagues informally or professionally such as the words Boss, Om, Bang, Mas, and Bro. The use of this language is less relevant for use in the scope of government organizations, especially the Indonesian Ministry of Defense. Likewise, the phenomenon occurs when employees of the Indonesian Ministry of Defense enter the office area using a car, some of them do not open the windows to answer greetings and return respect as a form of appreciation to the guard on duty. According to Prof. Dr. H.A. Rudiana, 2021 in Warsita 2008), Verbal Communication is information conveyed verbally or orally through what is spoken or spoken. And verbal information through words or sentences is called speaking/talking. This conversation can be used to express ideas, thoughts and something that the speaker feels. Examples in this case are voice mail, voice messages, small notes, electronic mail, and others. For symbols, language or messages in verbal communication, namely, all types of symbols that can be logos and concise images that express one or more meanings of words.

This verbal language can also be considered a spoken code system because verbal communication or oral communication is the most widely used in human interaction in expressing ideas, thoughts, emotions, information, and explanations, and can also be used to exchange thoughts and feelings, in debates and arguments. The problem in implementing communication ethics with an aesthetic touch in the art of communication is what is related to the misuse of oral communication in many conditions because ethics in communication can certainly also convey the various languages used by humans according to the basic principles of oral communication. Meanwhile, Non-Verbal Communication according to Prof. Dr. H.A. Rusdiana, 2021 is communication that uses gestures, movements, something, how to wear clothes or something else that can represent the wearer's feelings (expression), at the most important times for example: sad, happy, difficult, happy or depressed. Related to this, researchers also found a phenomenon in the field, namely that some employees of the Indonesian Ministry of Defense still do not respect or show poor body gestures when talking and meeting superiors or leaders, this is closely related to the identification of nonverbal communication, namely conceptually. In theory, it can be separated or distinguished between verbal/oral

communication and nonverbal/non-oral communication, although in reality these two types of communication represent each other, interweave and complement each other in the communication we do every day (Deddy Mulyana, 2005). Kinesic messages are non-verbal or non-verbal messages that use meaningful body movements, consisting of facial messages, gestural messages, and postural messages (Jalaludin Rakhmat, 1994).

According to Dr. Irwan, S.K.M., 2017 Ethics are rules of action and behavior in a particular society, a community or a social structure of society. Therefore, in-depth research on the analysis of employee communication ethics on the performance of the Civil Service Bureau of the Indonesian Ministry of Defense Secretariat is very relevant. By understanding how employees adapt to existing communication norms, organizations can identify potential improvements in appropriate communication training programs.

Organizational Communication

According to Hoveland (1948) defines communication, "The process by which an individual (the communicator) transmits stimuli (usually verbal symbols) to modify, the behavior of other individuals". (Communication is a process by which an individual transmits stimuli to influence or change the behavior of other individuals). Meanwhile, according to Everett M. Rogers and Lawrence Kicaid (1981), communication is a process when two or more individuals form and exchange information with each other, which in turn will lead to understanding and understanding that can be a guideline for behavior.

According to Yasir (2020) Communication is a process, as a symbolic activity and as a transaction of meaning.

According to Mathis and Jackson, "An organization is a social unit of a group of people who interact with each other according to a certain pattern so that each member of the organization has their functions and duties, as a unit that has a specific purpose and has clear boundaries so that it can be separated".

Organizational Communication

According to Goldhaber (1986), Organizational communication is a process of creating and exchanging messages in a network of social relationships that are connected to each other with the aim of overcoming uncertain situations and conditions that are full of dynamics of change. Meanwhile, Frank Jefkins (Ruslan, 2007) identifies in his definition that organizational communication is a form of communication that has been planned by a public community or wider society that is located where the public community or society is located to achieve certain goals. If the type of classification in this definition is taken as its essence, it will be understood that the actors of organizational communication are one of them, namely the organization as an institution, which means that it can be considered as a unity of opinion from the party that is faced with the target of communication outside of itself. Interaction or communication between members in an organization, interaction or communication between members and their leaders, and interaction or communication between members and other parties is what is called organizational communication.

Communication Ethics

Ethics comes from the Greek word "Ethos", which in its singular form means habit. Ethics is a form of art, philosophy, values, and morals and is not fixed/changeable according to point of view, depending on who the assessor is and how much experience he has and from this ethics is classified into good (ethical) and bad (unethical). Safrodin Halimi said, the general understanding of ethics is the understanding that ethics consists of four main things, namely as follows:

- 1) Viewed from the object, ethics is an effort to discuss philosophical reasons (rationing) about human behavior;
- 2) Viewed from the source, the source of ethics is reason and philosophy. As a result of human thought and creation, ethics is dynamic and does not apply to the whole;
- 3) Viewed from the function, the function of ethics is an assessor, determinant and filter of human behavior, whether the behavior is considered good or bad, noble or low calculated from the whole of human behavior. Ethics is a concept of thinking about idealistic values that are used to determine the prestige or status of human behavior. The study of ethics on the existing value system refers to the study of the moral value system in that society.
- 4) In terms of nature, ethics plays a greater role as a relatively dynamic concept, namely it can change according to the needs and standards of the moral value views of a social society.
 - a. Verbal Communication

According to Kusumawati (2015), the definition of Verbal Communication is a form of communication in the form of delivery between the communicator and the communicant through written or oral communication (verbal/oral). Verbal communication occupies a dominant portion because, in reality, ideas, notions, thoughts, or decisions are easier to convey than nonverbal. The hope is that the communicator (audience, who can be a listener or a reader) can more easily understand the message conveyed by the communicator. Another example of verbal communication is conversation which can also be done using media (telephone, radio, etc.). Verbal communication through writing can be done directly or indirectly between the communicator and the communicant/audience, the delivery of information is done using letters, paintings, pictures, graphics, codes, codes, and others.

- b. Nonverbal Communication.

However, according to Kusumawati (2015), nonverbal communication is a communication whose message is packaged in a form without words. In real life, nonverbal communication is sometimes considered less subtle to use, compared to verbal/oral communication. The use of nonverbal communication is carried out based on the norms that exist in a society.

Human Resources (Employees)

According to Schermerhorn (1996), Human Resources are humans as individuals, individuals, or groups that contribute to forming an organization in producing goods and services. According to Nawawi (2001), Human Resources are humans who work and have a function as an asset of an organization or company that can be calculated quantitatively. Human Resources are the main potential that drives an organization. According to Herbert J. Chrudden and Arthur W. Sherman (1996), Human Resource Management in several forms has existed and been

recognized since humans first discovered the benefits and value of working hard, working together, and being in a community, in this way humans find it easy to achieve their communal goals. According to KBBI, an employee is a person who works in a government system, which can be a company, office, organization, and so on. Meanwhile, the definition of a Civil Servant is every individual Indonesian citizen who has met the specified requirements, who is appointed by an authorized official and assigned certain tasks in a position within/abroad, or assigned other state tasks, and who is paid according to applicable laws and regulations.

The State Civil Apparatus, hereinafter abbreviated as ASN, is a profession for civil servants and Government Employees with Work Agreements who work in government agencies, carry out certain tasks, and are paid according to agreed provisions and existing laws and regulations. State Civil Apparatus Employees, hereinafter referred to as ASN Employees, are civil servants and Government Employees with Work Agreements who are appointed in their status by the Personnel Development Officer and then assigned tasks in a government position and assigned other state tasks and are paid according to applicable laws and regulations.

Government Employees with Work Agreements, hereinafter abbreviated as PPPK, are Indonesian citizens who meet certain requirements, who are appointed based on work agreements for a certain period according to the rules set by the Personnel Development Officer, to carry out government duties. PNS Kemhan are civil servants who serve in the Ministry of Defense and TNI whose guidance is the authority of the Minister of Tentara Nasional Indonesia, hereinafter abbreviated as TNI, are individuals from members of the Army, Navy, and Air Force. Employees of the Ministry of Defense, hereinafter referred to as Kemhan Employees, are Civil Servants and TNI Soldiers assigned to the Ministry of Defense who handle tasks according to the duties and functions of their work units and/or on the instructions of the Minister of Defense.

According to Article 2 of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 43 of 1999 concerning the Principles of Personnel, it is explained that those referred to as Civil Servants consist of; PNS members, TNI members and Polri members. And in the work environment of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia, there are elements of employees who man, namely TNI employees and PNS. In the Regulation of the Minister of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia No. 17 of 2019, it is stated that Civil Servants of the Ministry of Defense are Civil Servants who serve in the Ministry of Defense and the TNI, whose personnel development is the authority of the Minister of Defense through the Personnel Officer of the Work Unit where the person concerned serves. Therefore, the application of behavior related to tasks and organizational communication uses uniform and identical norms.

Method

The researcher chose the type of research using a qualitative method because the researcher wanted to know directly the opinions or responses obtained from informants, both key informants, main informants and supporting informants at the Bureau of Personnel, Secretariat General of the Indonesian Ministry of Defense.

Analysis Method and Data Collection Method

1) Interview method

According to Moleong (2018), an interview is a conversation and communication to achieve certain goals and objectives. The conversation was obtained by the interviewer and interviewee. In this study, the researcher conducted a direct interview method in the work environment of the Ministry of Defense's Secretariat General Personnel Bureau to obtain supporting data.

2) Observation

Creswell (2008) stated that the definition of observation is "Observation is the collection of data through who use of human sense. In some natural conditions, that observation will be the act of watching social phenomena in reality and recording every event as they happen", which means more or less "Observation is the collection of data using the function of the human senses. In some conditions, this observation will take the form of an action in the form of observing every social phenomenon in the real world and recording the events that occur.

Analysis of Employee Communication Ethics on The Performance of The Personnel Bureau of The General Secretary of The Ministry of Defense of The Republic of Indonesia

The Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia, abbreviated as Setjen Kemhan, is an assistant element to the leadership of the Ministry of Defense led by the Secretary-General. Setjen Kemhan is under and responsible to the Minister of Defense. Setjen Kemhan has the task of coordinating the implementation of tasks, coaching, and providing administrative support to all organizational units within the Ministry of Defense. In carrying out the tasks as referred to, Setjen Kemhan carries out the following functions:

1. Coordination of activities of the Ministry of Defense;
2. Coordination and preparation of plans and programs of the Ministry of Defense;
3. Guidance and provision of administrative support including administration, personnel, finance, household, archives, and documentation of the Ministry of Defense;
4. Guidance and implementation of the organization and procedures, cooperation, and public relations;
5. Coordination and preparation of laws and regulations and legal assistance;
6. Implementation of management of state property/assets; and
7. Implementation of other tasks assigned by the Minister of Defense

The Secretary General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia has the following vision: Realizing a strong, resilient, modern, and dynamic National Defense that can maintain and protect the existence of the nation and the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. With the following missions:

- a) Organizing the management of the national defense system in the form of determining general policies, planning, supervision, and control based on modern management

- b) Organizing the management of the strength and capabilities of the 3 (three) components of National Defense in a professional and modern manner through improving the existing coaching system, coordination, and synchronization with other government institutions and all components of the nation.
- c) Realizing the readiness and capabilities of national resources, national facilities, and infrastructure that have access to defense interests through coordination and synchronization with other government institutions and all components of the nation in the implementation of national development in a harmonious and integrated manner.
- d) Increasing foreign cooperation in the field of defense to support national interests, especially in participating in maintaining world peace.
- e) Increasing research and development of standard defense equipment, system arrangement, doctrine and operational procedures, and mobilization; by the development of modern defense science and technology through cooperation between universities and strategic industries.
- f) Improving the quality, transparency, and accountability of the State Defense apparatus through improving human resources and empowering internal control and supervision functions.

In the Regulation of the Minister of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2019 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Ministry of Defense, Article 9, the Secretariat General consists of:

- a) Planning and Finance Bureau;
- b) Personnel Bureau;
- c) Legal Bureau;
- d) Administration and Protocol Bureau;
- e) General Bureau;
- f) Public Relations Bureau;
- g) Organization and Implementation Bureau; and
- h) Legislation Bureau.

The Personnel Bureau, hereinafter referred to as Ropeg, is an implementing element of part of the Secretariat General's functions led by the Head of the Personnel Bureau, referred to as Karopeg, who has the task of formulating technical policies in the field of personnel, coaching and providing support for the ministry's personnel administration.

In carrying out the duties as referred to in Article 37, Ropeg carries out the following functions:

- a) Formulating technical policies in the field of personnel;
- b) Preparing plans for the needs of defense employees and procurement of defense civil servants;
- c) Preparation of job development, rank, transfer, planning and analysis of education and training needs for defense employees and defense civil servants at the TNI and TNI Army, TNI Navy, TNI Air Force headquarters;
- d) Career development of defense employees based on competency assessment;
- e) Mental, physical and welfare development of defense employees;
- f) Career, separation and distribution of defense employees;
- g) Implementation of defense employee data management; and

h) Management of bureau administration and household. Formulation of technical policies in the field of defense employee care and implementation of defense employee care.

Ropeg consists of:

- a) Main Civil Servant Section;
- b) Employee Procurement and Development Section;
- c) Employee Career Section;
- d) Employee Care Section; and
- e) Functional Position Group.

The PNS Main Section hereinafter referred to as the PNS Main Section is led by the Head of the PNS Main Section referred to as the Head of the PNS Main Section has the task of carrying out the preparation of technical policy formulation in the field of PNS development, preparation of needs and procurement plans, mutations, functional position development and enforcement of discipline for PNS Kemhan. In carrying out the duties as referred to in Article 40, the PNS Main Section carries out the following functions:

- a) Preparation of technical policy formulation in the field of PNS;
- b) Management of databases and preparation of proposals for PNS Kemhan formations;
- c) Preparation of transfer proposals

Analysis of Communication Ethics of Employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia in Using Verbal Communication

Based on the data obtained, verbal communication in the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia shows a pattern that reflects strong ethical aspects. Employees in communicating tend to use polite, clear language and respect existing authorities. For example, in a meeting or instruction situation, employees tend to use language that shows respect for superiors or leaders, such as using appropriate and non-offensive words. In addition, in the context of conveying information to the public or stakeholders, verbal communication is carried out transparently and honestly, prioritizing public interests over personal or group interests.

Honesty and integrity are also reflected in the way employees convey reports, evaluation results, or other important information. They tend to avoid manipulating data or presenting misleading information for the sake of personal or group interests. This is in line with the theory of communication ethics which emphasizes the importance of honesty, integrity, and transparency in communicating in an organizational environment.

In addition, verbal communication in the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia also reflects a sense of responsibility in the use of words. Employees try not to spread gossip or unverified information, paying attention to the accuracy and truth of the information conveyed. This indicates that employees understand the importance of being responsible for what they communicate, which is in accordance with the principles of communication ethics in the organization.

In the context of employee relations, verbal communication also reflects respect for the diversity of opinions and ideas. Employees tend to listen carefully before responding, avoiding dominating or belittling others. This reflects respect and fairness in communication, which are important aspects of communication ethics in organizations.

The theory of communication ethics in organizations highlights the importance of moral principles and values in communication interactions in the work environment. According to Treviño and Nelson (2016), communication ethics in organizations include ethical considerations in producing, interpreting, and delivering messages. This includes honesty, integrity, respect, responsibility, and other moral values that form the basis of ethical behavior in communication. Research by Arnaud (2010) emphasizes the importance of awareness of ethics in organizational communication, which involves not only the words used but also body language, tone of voice, and the overall context of communication.

Several studies have been conducted to understand how communication ethics affect organizational performance and culture. For example, research by DeGeorge (2010) highlights the importance of honest, open, and transparent communication in creating an ethical and productive work environment. Likewise, research by Jones (2012) reveals that organizations that prioritize ethics in communication tend to have higher levels of job satisfaction and fewer internal problems related to conflict or confusion.

In addition, verbal communication in the Bureau of Personnel, Secretariat General of the Indonesian Ministry of Defense shows a pattern that reflects strong ethical aspects. Employees tend to use polite, clear language in communicating, and respect existing authorities. For example, in meeting or instruction situations, employees tend to use words that show respect for superiors or leaders, such as using appropriate and non-offensive words. In addition, in the context of conveying information to the public or stakeholders, verbal communication is carried out transparently and honestly, prioritizing public interests above personal or group interests.

Honesty and integrity are also reflected in the way employees convey reports, evaluation results, or other important information. They tend to avoid manipulating data or presenting misleading information for the benefit of certain individuals or groups. This is in line with the theory of communication ethics that emphasizes the importance of honesty, integrity, and transparency in communicating in an organizational environment. huhu

In addition, verbal communication in the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia also reflects a sense of responsibility in the use of words. Employees try not to spread gossip or unverified information, paying attention to the accuracy and truth of the information conveyed. This indicates that employees understand the importance of being responsible for what they communicate, which is to the principles of communication ethics in the organization. The diversity of opinions and ideas. Employees tend to listen carefully before responding, avoiding dominating or belittling others. This reflects respect and fairness in communication, which are important aspects of communication ethics in organizations.

Based on the theory of communication ethics in organizations, it emphasizes the importance of moral principles and values in communication interactions in the work

environment. According to Treviño and Nelson (2016), communication ethics in organizations include ethical considerations in producing, interpreting, and delivering messages. This includes honesty, integrity, respect, responsibility, and other moral values that form the foundation of ethical behavior in communication. Research by Arnaud (2010) emphasizes the importance of awareness of ethics in organizational communication, which involves not only the words used but also body language, tone of voice, and the overall context of communication.

Higher levels of job satisfaction and fewer internal problems related to conflict or confusion.

Analysis of the communication ethics of employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia in using verbal communication reflects the crucial role of effective communication in an organizational environment. Effective communication is the main foundation for conveying vital information to employees, including work instructions, organizational goals, individual roles, and problem-solving. The importance of effective communication is evident in creating synergy between departments and personnel, leading to the implementation of good and well-coordinated human resource (HR) management. Based on the available data, several aspects influence the effectiveness of verbal communication in the Bureau of Personnel, including:

This is following the Organizational Communication Theory by McShane and Von Glinow (2018) which states that an effective communication approach involves the use of clear language, an orderly communication structure, and the appropriateness of the message to its audience. In the context of the Bureau of Personnel, employees need to understand the importance of using appropriate, unambiguous language and following established communication protocols.

Research by Robbins and Judge (2017) shows that education and morals play an important role in shaping a person's communication ethics. Employees who have a good education tend to be better able to articulate messages clearly and avoid misunderstandings. In addition, strong morals help ensure ethical communication and respect for organizational values. Meanwhile, the theory of social interaction in the context of organizations (Turner, 2019) highlights the importance of positive relationships between employees. Good interactions create a harmonious work environment and support effective communication. Good relationships also strengthen a sense of togetherness and mutual trust between individuals. From the perspective of organizational management theory (Daft, 2018), a clear understanding of the organization's vision, mission, and values helps direct communication with clear goals. Employees who fully understand the organization can convey messages in the right context and follow the strategic direction that has been set.

In the context of the Personnel Bureau, the use of effective verbal communication requires an awareness of communication ethics, clarity of message, adjustment to the audience, as well as moral integrity, and a strong understanding of the organization. With the implementation of these effective communication principles, it is hoped that a productive, harmonious work environment will be created that can achieve organizational goals optimally.

In addition, the communication ethics of employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia in using verbal communication highlights the important role of effective communication in improving performance and efficiency in the organizational environment. Based on the data obtained, it can be concluded that good communication plays a central role in conveying clear and precise information to each member of the organization. This includes work instructions, organizational targets, individual roles, and solving problems that arise. Furthermore, the effectiveness of communication also affects the synergy between parts of the organization, allows for efficient interoperability, and supports targeted HR Management in accordance with the organization's vision and mission. The key factors that drive the success of effective communication in the Bureau of Personnel include the quality of human resources, a deep understanding of the organization and its goals, and the creation of open and structured dialogue between superiors and subordinates in achieving predetermined performance targets.

Organizational communication theory regarding communication effectiveness emphasizes the importance of message suitability to the organizational context, a clear communication structure, and a deep understanding of the audience. According to McShane and Von Glinow (2018), effective communication in an organization requires the use of appropriate language, a regular communication framework, and the suitability of messages to organizational goals and employee needs.

Research by Robbins and Judge (2017) highlights the importance of quality human resources in supporting effective communication. Human resources who are skilled, trained, and have a good understanding of the organization tend to be able to communicate better, avoid misunderstandings, and support the creation of a productive work environment.

Organizational management theory by Daft (2018) emphasizes that a deep understanding of the vision, mission, and values of the organization helps form directed and effective communication. Employees who understand the goals of the organization will have the ability to convey messages with the appropriate context and follow the strategic direction that has been established. A structured open dialogue approach between superiors and subordinates is also an important part of effective communication. This is following the theory of social interaction in the context of organizations which highlights the importance of positive and open relationships between individuals (Turner, 2019).

Analysis of the communication ethics of employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia in using verbal communication reveals the importance of effective communication in the context of the organization, especially in the Bureau of Human Resources of the Ministry of Defense. Communication in organizations has the main purpose of conveying messages to build good relationships individually, in groups, and in the organization as a whole. This plays a key role in increasing productivity, resolving conflicts, developing employee potential, and creating a conducive and professional work environment. Communication ethics, both in verbal aspects and ethical concepts inspired by the TNI environment, are also important factors in achieving the desired communication goals.

According to organizational communication theory, the main purpose of communication in an organization is to achieve a common understanding between the parties involved in the communication process (Robbins & Judge, 2017). In the context of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense, communication objectives include delivering work instructions, organizational goals, individual roles, and resolving problems that arise in the work environment. Effective communication in achieving these goals plays a central role in maintaining harmony and productivity within an organization.

A study by McShane and Von Glinow (2018) emphasized that effective communication within an organization plays an important role in increasing productivity, supporting appropriate decision-making, and building harmonious relationships between members of the organization. In the Human Resources Bureau of the Ministry of Defense, good communication enables management to manage human resources efficiently, resolve conflicts effectively, and build a work environment conducive to employee development.

The ethical aspect of communication is also an important focus in this analysis. Communication ethics refers to moral norms that govern the communication behavior of individuals or groups within an organization (Daft, 2018). In the Civil Service Bureau of the Ministry of Defense Secretariat General, the concept of communication ethics inspired by the TNI environment, such as professionalism, loyalty, integrity, and exemplary behavior, is the basis for implementing effective communication.

The implementation of effective communication in the Civil Service Bureau requires adaptation to the strategic goals of the organization. This includes a good merit system in employee management, ASN professionalism, and efficient personnel services. By strengthening healthy relationships between employees and the organization, effective communication facilitates the achievement of predetermined organizational goals.

The analysis of the communication ethics of employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia in using verbal communication highlights the importance of the concept of ethics in verbal communication in the work environment. The concept of ethics in verbal communication, especially in the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense, includes the use of appropriate language both orally and in writing. Ethics in verbal communication aims to convey information correctly and build good cooperation between individuals, groups, and organizations. This is reflected in the use of polite language, respect for work relations, and the adoption of terminology that is respectful from the TNI environment. Verbal communication ethics also involve the use of polite and respectful words, as well as handling communication situations that pay attention to time, delivery methods, and appropriate procedures. Overall, the concept of ethics in verbal communication helps ensure harmonious, professional, and effective relationships in the organizational work environment. According to communication theory, ethics in communication are moral principles that govern the communication behavior of individuals or groups in a context (Daft, 2018). In the context of the Bureau of Personnel, verbal communication ethics are very important because they concern how information is conveyed correctly and respectfully. Research by Johnson and Hackman (2018) emphasizes that the use of polite and respectful

language in verbal communication can increase work effectiveness and strengthen relationships between individuals in the organization. Communication theory suggests that the use of appropriate language is a key aspect of verbal communication (Robbins & Judge, 2017). In the Bureau of Personnel, the use of polite, clear, and respectful language is important to maintain the ethics of verbal communication. Research by Brown and Levinson (1987) also highlights

The analysis of the communication ethics of employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia in using verbal communication highlights practices that reflect ethical values in the context of daily work. In the Bureau of Personnel, verbal communication is implemented by paying attention to values such as honesty, responsibility, and integrity. Honesty is reflected in the delivery of information that is not twisted or hidden, responsibility is manifested through readiness to carry out tasks well, and integrity is demonstrated through consistency in behavior in accordance with the moral and ethical principles of the organization.

Communication theory states that ethical communication involves the use of honest, polite, and respectful language (Brown & Levinson, 1987). In the context of the Bureau of Personnel, honesty in verbal communication is important for building trust between employees and the organization. Research by Gudykunst and Ting-Toomey (1988) also shows that communication that reflects honesty can increase work effectiveness and strengthen healthy working relationships.

Responsibility in verbal communication includes readiness to carry out tasks well and be responsible for the information conveyed. The theory of responsibility in communication states that individuals who are responsible in communication tend to be more respected and trusted (Robbins & Judge, 2017). Research by Johnson and Hackman (2018) emphasizes the importance of responsibility in communication to achieve organizational goals effectively.

Integrity in verbal communication in the Bureau of Personnel is demonstrated through consistency in behavior that is in accordance with the moral and ethical values of the organization. According to communication theory, integrity in communication refers to the congruence between an individual's words and actions (McShane & Von Glinow, 2018). Research by O'Hair et al. (2015) shows that integrity in communication is a key factor in building a professional work environment and strengthening trust among members of the organization.

Although there are still challenges in implementing ethical communication practices, steps such as providing affirmation regarding tasks and functions, strengthening understanding of ethical values, and giving members trust to carry out tasks in accordance with their honesty and integrity, are efforts taken to achieve communication that reflects ethical values in the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia.

The application of verbal communication ethics in the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia has a significant positive impact on organizational performance. First, the application of verbal communication ethics allows for increased collaboration between employees. Good collaboration is based on effective and respectful communication between individuals and groups in the organization (Robbins & Judge, 2017). In the Personnel Bureau, honest, open communication ethics that

respect the opinions of others can improve employees' ability to work together synergistically, produce better solutions, and achieve common goals efficiently. Second, the application of verbal communication ethics also contributes to increased productivity at work. Management theories show that effective communication facilitates the flow of appropriate information and helps reduce misunderstandings and communication barriers (McShane & Von Glinow, 2018). Thus, communication practices that follow ethical principles can improve efficiency and productivity in carrying out daily tasks in the Personnel Bureau. Third, verbal communication ethics can also reduce conflict in the work environment. Honest, open communication that respects differences of opinion can reduce the potential for interpersonal conflict (Brown & Levinson, 1987). In the context of the Personnel Bureau, communication practices that pay attention to ethics can help manage conflict better, facilitate constructive dialogue, and create a more harmonious work environment. Fourth, the application of verbal communication ethics also triggers increased innovation in the organization. Innovation theory emphasizes the importance of open and respectful collaboration and the exchange of ideas to spark creativity and innovation (Johnson & Hackman, 2018). With communication practices that prioritize ethics, employees at the Personnel Bureau can feel more comfortable sharing ideas, making suggestions, and contributing to the organization's innovation process. Fifth, the application of verbal communication ethics forms stronger relationships among employees. Honest, open, and respectful communication builds trust and reduces the communication gap between superiors and subordinates (Robbins & Judge, 2017). In the context of the Personnel Bureau, strong relationships between employees can increase job satisfaction, motivation, and loyalty to the organization. Finally, verbal communication ethics.

Conclusion

The communication ethics applied by the employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia positively influence verbal communication in the environment. This is supported by the observation that verbal communication in the Bureau of Personnel reflects a strong pattern in ethical aspects, such as the use of polite, clear language, respect for authority, and showing honesty, integrity, and responsibility in conveying information. The application of communication ethics not only improves the quality of verbal communication but also creates an effective, harmonious, and productive work environment. This is also evident from the communication practices observed in various contexts, including the use of online media that support the accessibility of information and strengthen ethical principles in online communication. Thus, strong communication ethics practices in the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia contribute positively to verbal communication and strengthen the basis for creating a more effective and ethical work environment. 2. The communication ethics of the employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia towards nonverbal communication, it can be concluded that nonverbal communication plays a crucial role in maintaining integrity, authority, and respecting the

principles of the code of ethics in the Ropeg environment of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense. Nonverbal communication highlights the importance of body language, gestures, and respectful attitudes as essential elements in building a positive and harmonious image within an organization. Practices such as communication training and adaptation to work environment norms have proven effective in increasing understanding and awareness of body language and sensitivity to the nonverbal expressions of others. Thus, nonverbal communication based on ethics can be a key driver in creating an efficient, harmonious, and ethically sound work environment in the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia. 3. The application of communication ethics through the principles of communication ethics for employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia illustrates a broad positive impact, covering aspects of organizational culture, integrity, and public trust. By maintaining the principles and core values based on communication ethics, employees of the Bureau of Personnel of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia can create an inclusive, transparent, and responsible work culture. The theory of moral behavior and the implementation of a code of ethics in an organization highlight the importance of consistency in implementing ethical principles in every daily interaction. Strategies such as ethics and code of ethics training, fostering organizational values, and providing incentives for employees who demonstrate a commitment to ethics, are the foundation for building a work culture with high integrity. Thus, the application of communication ethics through the principles of communication ethics for employees of the Civil Service Bureau of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia not only provides internal benefits for the organization but also creates a significant positive impact on the surrounding environment and stakeholders involved.

References

- Abidin, K., & Wandu, W. (2023). Communication Ethics between Students and Lecturers in Academic Interaction through Digital Media. *MEDIALOG: Journal of Communication Science*, 6(1), 47-61.
- Agung, A. F. (2023). Effectiveness of Organizational Communication in Resolving Right of Reply News in Public Relations Section of Bekasi City Regional Secretariat. *DECISION: Journal of Public Administration*, 5(01), 30-44.
- Aprilia, I. A. (2022). The Role of Government Communication in Realizing Good Governance Through Public Services. *Communication*, 13(1), 70-85.
- Banks, S. (2015). The Role of Nonverbal Communication in Workplace Interactions. *Journal of Business Communication*, 52(2), 223-245. doi:10.1177/0021943614561653.
- Pease, A., & Pease, B. (2004). *The definitive book of body language*. Bantam Books.
- Jones, T., & LeBaron, M. (2002). *Resolving Workplace Conflict: Four Ways to a Win-Win Solution*. Wiley.
- Civil Servant Code of Ethics of the Republic of Indonesia. Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010.

- DR HA Rusdiana, M. M. (2021). *Organizational Communication Ethics: Philosophy, Concepts and Applications*. Uin Sgd Bandung Research and Publishing Center.
- Effendhie, M. (2011). *Introduction to Organization*. *Organizational Governance and Archives*, 1-90.
- Ekman, P. (1973). *Cross-cultural studies of facial expression*. *Darwin and facial expression: A century of research in review*, 169-222.
- Fahmi, R. F. (2022). *Communication Strategy of Civil Service Agency and Human Resource Development in Digitalization of Civil Servant Promotion Services*. *Peurawi Journal: Islamic Communication Study Media*, 5(1), 63-100.
- Febianti, F. (2020). *The Role of Public Relations in Organizational Communication in Libraries*. *Journal of Librarianship Studies Volume 2*, 79-94.
- Guidelines for the Implementation of Pancasila Values in the Ministry of Defense*. Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia.
- Hall, E. T. (1966). *The hidden dimension*.
- Karina, Y., & Rustiana, A. (2019). *Application of Communication Ethics in Preparing Professionalism in the World of Work*. *Economic Education Analysis Journal*, 8(1), 389-403.
- KM, I. S. (2020). *Ethics and Health Behavior*. *Absolute Media*.
- Kurniati, M. (2022). *Analysis of Civil Servant Communication Style of Millennial Generation in State Civil Service Agency*. *Civil Service Journal*, 16(2 Nov), 56-76.
- Matsumoto, D., Keltner, D., Shiota, M. N., Frank, M. G., & O'Sullivan, M. (2008). *Facial expressions of emotion*. *Handbook of emotions*, 211-234.
- Mehrabian, A. (1971). *Silent messages*. Wadsworth.
- Muchtar, M., Hermana, D., Hanifah, H. S., & Anggraeni, W. A. (2023). *The Role of Government Communication Media and Bureaucratic Behavior in Public Services (Study in Tarogong Kaler District, Garut)*. *Professional: Journal of Communication and Public Administration*, 10(1), 179-188.
- Nasrullah, N., Askolani, A., & Sutrisna, A. (2023). *The Influence of Organizational Communication on Employee Performance: (Census of Employees of PT Nata Bersaudara Sejahtera)*. *Mufakat: Journal of Economics, Management and Accounting*, 2(5), 212-223.
- rahmadaniah. (2014). *Employee Communication Ethics in Providing Services to Customers at PT. Globalindo 21 Express Samarinda Branch*. *eJournal of Communication Science*, 353-369.
- Solomon, R. C. (1992). *Corporate Roles, Personal Virtues: An Aristotelean Approach to Business Ethics*. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 2(3), 317-339.
- Sugiyono, S. (2016). *Quantitative, qualitative, R&D research methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- The 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia*.
- Treviño, L. K., & Brown, M. (2005). *Ethical Decision Making in Organizations: A Person-Situation Interactionist Model*. *Academy of Management Review*, 30(4), 715-734.
- Ulya, E. D., Saleh, A., & Priatna, W. B. (2016). *Application of Interpersonal Communication Ethics to IPB Diploma Program Students*. *Journal of Development Communication*, 14(1).

- Utama, D. Z. M., & SE, M. (2020). Human Resource Management: Basic Concepts and Theories. UNJ PRESS.
- Wiryanto. (2004). Introduction to Communication Science. Publisher PT Gramedia Widiasarana Indonesia.
- Yasir. (2020). Introduction to Communication Science: A Critical and Comprehensive Approach. Yogyakarta: CV BUDI UTAMA.

